

The Impact of Maximum Power Point Tracking Algorithms on Properties of On-chip PV-based Energy Harvester for IoT devices

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Abstract: This article presents the analysis of selected maximum power point tracking (MPPT) algorithms and their influence on developed energy harvester (EH) system under uniform conditions. The energy harvester is an electronic system that converts available ambient energy to electrical energy and regulates its distribution to the output. The aim is to design a energy harvester with highest integration rate possible with consideration of area requirements and low power consumption. To improve the overall energy conversion of the developed harvester, we implemented several MPPT algorithms (Pilot Cell, Constant Voltage, Perturb & Observe) into a dedicated MPPT controller that controls the DC-DC converter. Consequently, we experimentally analyzed their impact on the harvester system. Findings shows that even simple algorithms with smaller chip area and lower power consumption can achieve results comparable to more complex ones. The proposed, manufactured and experimentally evaluated EH chip prototype has proven its expected functionality, and is therefore, fully capable of supplying energy for low-power electronics and battery-operated devices.

Keywords: Energy Harvester; MPPT algorithms; Conversion Efficiency; Perturb&Observe; Constant Voltage; Pilot-Cell

1. Introduction and Motivation

The research and development of electronics is mostly driven forward by actual needs of human society but it is limited by materials and technologies of the given time. Materials and technologies are the dominant factors influencing the miniaturization of electronic systems or their level of integration on a chip. Reducing physical dimensions of components on a chip has positive effect on the power consumption, while increasing the density of components brings more computing power [1]. These properties enable the emergence of smart and wireless electronics such as Internet of Things (IoT) or wearable electronics.

Recently, we are approaching a point where to provide enough of computing power in a small area is no longer issue for many applications. On the other hand, using energy sources more effectively and decrease energy consumption are becoming more and more important. Wearable electronics or IoT make extensive use of various sensor systems for which a permanent source of electrical energy is unavailable and therefore, are powered by batteries. Battery-powered systems have a finite lifespan influenced by their own energy consumption and battery capacity. When the battery is discharged, it needs to be recharged or replaced. In case of wearable electronics, this is of course not a problem but in other applications like sensor systems in hard-to-reach places or implantable medical devices, such maintenance is either rather demanding or impossible. Therefore, it would be beneficial to avoid recharging/replacing batteries altogether.

Energy harvesters (EH) are the solution to extension of the battery system lifespan [2]. EH is a system that harvests ambient energy from various sources (e.g. solar, thermal,

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mechanical, etc.) and converts it into electrical energy. High output power is often used in practice employing energy harvesters that convert solar energy into electrical one. Energy harvesting systems generally consist of an energy converter, a circuit that adapts the output voltage value (most often a DC-DC converter), and an energy storage that serves as the main energy source and a place where the excess converted energy is stored. Due to nonlinear characteristics of Photo-Voltaic (PV) cells or the inability to adapt to load changes, such a harvesting system is not able to function properly and independently or offer the maximum energy conversion efficiency, and therefore, the presence of a control circuit is necessary. In terms of simplicity, this can be either a Pulse-Width Modulated (PWM) regulator that drives a power switch for energy distribution from the solar cells to the load or batteries. More advanced option is to apply DC-DC converter to provide more stable energy distribution using direct PWM/PFM control or enhanced circuit providing the maximum power point tracking (MPPT).

There are several known algorithms that can tune the EH operating point, which approaches or overlaps the maximum power point (MPP). The MPP tuning should take as little time as possible to eliminate the MPP drift, eliminate deformations of the PV cell characteristics under partially shaded conditions or adapt to material degradation due to overheating or aging. The solution to each of the above-mentioned problems increases the complexity of the MPPT algorithm, which leads to robustness of the respective digital circuit and increase in the energy consumption and chip area overhead [3–5]. Digital circuits providing the MPPT control are generally less energy-hungry and occupy significantly less chip area compared to analog circuits, but despite these facts, their increase in total energy consumption can disable the whole energy harvester. Additionally, if they are very complex, the area overhead might be unacceptably large. Based on this information, one may conclude that when developing an energy harvester, it is necessary to take into account several parameters and make a compromise between them. This work therefore focuses on the analysis of selected MPPT algorithms and their impact on the entire energy harvester system in terms of several important aspects.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 1 brings motivation for the analysis of selected MPPT algorithms and their impact on the developed energy harvester. Section 2 describes energy harvesting systems for low-power electronics and offers comparison of selected energy converters in terms of the main parameters. Section 3 presents typical types of energy regulation that can be implemented in solar energy harvesting systems. Section 4 provides introduction into indirect and direct MPPT algorithms and summarizes advantages and disadvantages of each. General structure of the on-chip EH system (implemented in 65 nm CMOS technology) is described in Section 5, which also explains other used off-chip components to test the whole system. Evaluation of prototyped EH system chip samples using robust measurement setup and achieved results are presented Section 6. Discussion about the measured properties of each implemented MPPT algorithm within the EH system is given in Section 7. The final section concludes the key findings and options for possible future improvements.

2. Energy Harvesters

Energy harvesters are not a newly emerging concept. On the contrary, they are well-known and widely utilized in the form of photovoltaic, hydro or wind power plants, which convert solar/mechanical energy into electrical one, typically ranging from kilowatts to megawatts, and this capacity continues to grow.

As for devices more accessible for the general public, energy harvesters have appeared in products like calculators and LED lights. However, in recent years, they are increasingly found in more complex low-power electronics and systems-on-chip (SoC). Thus, for purposes of this paper, on-chip EH systems will be considered. As mentioned in Section 1, the enhancement of computational power and the reduction of energy consumption open doors for the development of sensor systems, wearable electronics and IoT devices. A critical component of such systems from energy point of view is typically the power

source, namely the battery. Its ability of supplying the energy to a system is time-limited and depends on the value of electrical load and ambient conditions. By utilizing energy harvesters, it is possible to extend the lifespan of battery-powered systems or in special cases, even completely replace them.

A significant advantage of energy harvesters for low-power electronics is the possibility of applying other types of energy converters (EC), such as piezoelectric or radio frequency (RF) ones, in addition to those already mentioned. It is also useful to combine more converters to create so-called hybrid energy harvesting systems. These systems are more likely to be capable of supplying electrical energy for longer periods of time or they may be able to provide power under conditions where a stand-alone converter would no longer have the necessary efficiency (such as a photovoltaic converter in the dark).

Energy harvesters are widely applicable systems but the choice of the appropriate type of harvester depends on the specific application. When selecting parameters such as the final location as well as available surrounding energy sources that can be converted into electrical energy, the value of the voltage generated by the respective converter, its output power density, and last but not least, the physical dimensions must be considered.

In terms of the mentioned parameters, the most commonly used energy converter in EH systems is a solar cell. The output voltage of a standalone solar cell typically ranges in hundreds of millivolts, and by simply connecting multiple cells in series, one can achieve a voltage in the range of volts, which is suitable for many integrated circuits. The energy conversion efficiency is approximately 25% and in some cases, it can reach up to 50% [?]. Despite the relatively low efficiency, the available power density is in hundreds of mW/m^2 , which provides sufficient energy for many low-power electronic systems. A comparison of parameters of selected energy converters with the PV converter is shown in Tab. 1 [6–11].

Table 1. Comparison of selected energy converters in terms of main parameters.

	Photovoltaic	Thermoelectric	Piezoelectric	RF
Output voltage	$\approx 600\text{ mV}$	$10 - 100\text{ mV}$	$1 - 100\text{ V}$	$1 - 4\text{ V}$
Energy	100 mW (outside)	$50 - 100\ \mu\text{W}/m^2$ (C)	15 W	0.0002 – 1 W
Efficiency	15 – 25%	1 – 13%	50 – 90%	1 – 90%

3. PV Energy System Regulation

The most commonly converted energy using an energy harvester is solar energy, due to the properties mentioned earlier. By connecting solar cells in series, one can achieve a higher output voltage, or by connecting them in parallel, a higher output current. Adjusting the output power from solar cells, whether on the voltage or current side, is a certain adaptation of the input conditions for the load. However, direct connection of PV cells to the load is inefficient and even dangerous, potentially leading to destructive effects. Thus, inserting a regulator between the solar cell and load can significantly prevent potential damage to the load. Furthermore, using a regulator might increase the efficiency of energy harvesting.

Just as the input conditions for the energy harvester change over time, so do the load conditions. Therefore, the role of a regulator is to adjust properties of the energy harvester to eliminate changes in conditions, whether at the input or output, to the greatest extent possible, for example, through pulse-width modulation (PWM) or more advanced methods of tracking the maximum power point of the EH system.

3.1. PWM Regulator

A straightforward method for controlling the distribution of energy from the energy harvester input to load or battery storage, is based on direct connection/disconnection of PV cells to the load. Its block diagram is shown in Fig. 1. PWM regulator adjusts the

amount of power transmitted to the output of the energy harvester by driving the power switch, however, it does not adapt the output voltage. To achieve the highest possible EH efficiency, the voltage generated at the input of the energy harvester must be equal to (or close to) the voltage of the charged battery storage.

Figure 1. Block diagram of PV energy harvester with a PWM controller.

Under very high load or when the battery storage is depleted, the PWM regulator (controller) adjusts its output so that the current flowing to the load is unrestricted, meaning it is regulated solely by the load itself. As the load decreases (or as batteries are charged), the duty cycle of the pulse-width modulated signal is adjusted, leading to a gradual disconnection from the input.

Simplicity of such a system positively impacts the cost, making it attractive for various applications. It can reliably transfer energy from the energy harvester input to its output and adapt to changing conditions at both the input and output of the energy harvester. During periods of excess solar energy, particularly in the summer, the system operates with high efficiency. At first glance, PWM regulation seems to be a suitable choice for any practical applications where cost is a primary concern. However, it is important to consider also the drawbacks of this regulation method. One of these is the number and configuration of solar cells necessary. Excessively, high charging power with very depleted batteries can negatively affect the lifespan of the battery storage. Last but not least, PWM regulator is unable to ensure full charge of the energy storage or sufficient voltage level for reliable operation of the powered system.

3.2. DC-DC Converter

An energy harvester with PWM regulator adjusts the output power but cannot control the output voltage. This voltage depends on the number of solar cells, their interconnection, and the intensity of incoming sunlight but generally, is limited mainly by connecting the solar cells in series.

To overcome the low voltage limit imposed by the number of solar cells in series, it is necessary to insert a DC-DC converter between the energy harvester and the electrical load or energy storage, as illustrated in Fig. 2. For the DC-DC converter to operate optimally and efficiently, it must be controlled by an additional circuit, for example MPPT controller.

Figure 2. Block diagram of energy harvester with a MPPT controller.

3.2.1. PWM/PFM control

DC-DC converters are commonly controlled by Pulse-Width Modulated (PWM) or Pulse-Frequency Modulated (PFM) signal. They secure a suitable output voltage by adjusting the duty cycle or frequency.

In the first case, the PWM is a technique for generating a signal whose period (T) is constant. The dynamic change of duty cycle (ratio of the duration of Log.1 (T_{on}) to the duration of one period) is obtained by change of T_{on} .

In the second case, the PFM generates a signal with fixed duration of Log.1 (T_{on}) and variable duration of Log.0. This way the frequency (and period) of the control signal is adjusted. For a better idea, the Fig. 3 display the waveform of the PWM and PFM signals.

Figure 3. PWM and PFM signal waveforms.

3.2.2. MPPT control

The main role of the MPPT regulator is to evaluate the measured input parameters, specifically voltage and current, and to adjust or shift the operating point on the power-voltage (P-V) curve of the solar cell (Fig. 4) to the maximum power point that can be obtained under given conditions, thereby maximizing energy extraction and the efficiency of the energy harvester.

Figure 4. P-V curve of a solar cell and MPP tracking.

In regulating the output power of the energy harvester, a wide range of algorithms exist, each suitable for a specific application. Simpler algorithms only need to measure one of the input parameters, voltage or current, and achieve high tuning speeds of the operating point, albeit at the cost of never reaching the actual V_{mpp} value. More complex algorithms for precise regulation and achieving higher efficiency require providing both variables, and it is possible to expand the inputs to include information about the intensity of ambient light irradiation or temperature.

Obtaining and processing input data is one thing but adapting the output voltage of the DC-DC converter based on this information is another. Such a voltage adaptation is achieved by generating so-called Pulse Frequency Modulated (PFM) or Pulse Width Modulated (PWM) control signal. In the case of PFM, the output voltage of the DC-DC converter is regulated by changing the frequency of the control signal. To achieve the highest possible voltage level, the higher frequency must be ensured. High frequency negatively impacts power consumption of the system, increases switching losses and electromagnetic interference, and consequently, decreases the overall efficiency.

The second option is PWM regulation, which operates with constant control signal frequency, and the duty cycle changes. Since the switching frequency is constant, it is accompanied by constant losses what creates an imaginary boundary between PWM and PFM to choose the right control signal modulation method.

A constant switching frequency is accompanied by constant losses, which when small in relation to the transmitted power, make PWM control more efficient than PFM. On the other hand, if the value of the transmitted power is small, the losses when switching at a constant frequency can exceed this value and such control becomes inefficient.

The general power ranges and efficiency levels, for which the selected type of modulation of the control signal is suitable, are shown in Fig. 5 [12–14].

Figure 5. Power efficiency of PFM and PWM vs load current.

4. MPPT Algorithms

The most commonly used energy converter is the solar cell due to its relatively high output voltage, provided power density and stability of the output power. Its current-voltage (I-V) characteristic or power-voltage (P-V) relationship, is non-linear and typically contains only one maximum, as shown in Fig. 4. When the operating point is located at the MPP on the P-V curve, we say that the system is tuned for the maximum energy extraction. The position of the operating point is determined by parameters such as the amount of incoming radiation on PV cells or the size of load. Since these conditions change dynamically, the position of the operating point shifts uncontrollably and may lead to inefficient energy extraction and potentially disabling the entire system. To control and set the operating point to MPP position, the aforementioned PWM regulator is commonly used, due to its simplicity. To obtain higher power conversion efficiency and higher accuracy, the more advanced regulator based on MPPT algorithms[15] can be implemented. Based on the type of inputs and the method of tuning the operating point, MPPT algorithms can be categorized into two groups: indirect and direct algorithms.

4.1. Indirect Algorithms

Indirect MPPT algorithms can be described as algorithms that primarily work with static variables. They process information from a general model or data obtained from pre-application characterization of the PV cell. This involves laboratory measurements acquired from the I-V and P-V curves in an unloaded state, from which we can extract important parameters such as open-circuit voltage V_{OV} , short-circuit current I_{SC} , and voltage V_{MPP} and current I_{MPP} at the MPP.

Based on the obtained data, it is possible to achieve the proper setting of the operating point of the energy converter for the maximum energy extraction. However, it is not possible to dynamically respond to changes in input conditions caused by factors such as changes in illumination, partial shading of the PV cell, and last but not least, material degradation due to aging. Individual indirect algorithms, by their very nature, will never reach the actual MPP but will approach and oscillate in its vicinity.

Despite the aforementioned drawbacks of indirect algorithms, some of them are very interesting for many applications. For example, algorithms like Constant Voltage (CV)[16], Pilot-cell (PC), Fractional Open Circuit Voltage (FOCV), Fractional Short Circuit Current (FSCC)[17], and others dominate in speed of tuning the operating point and are hardware-simple, which means they are not demanding in terms of area size and electrical energy consumption.

4.2. Direct Algorithms

Direct MPPT algorithms continuously adjust the operational point of the energy harvester based on real-time measurements of voltage V_{PV} and current I_{PV} , and thus

power P_{PV} , using an analog-to-digital converter. They do not require disconnecting the solar cell from the rest of the circuit, as is the case with some indirect algorithms.

Additionally, in contrast to indirect MPPT algorithms, direct MPPT algorithms do not require absolute knowledge of the I-V and P-V curves of the solar cell. Instead, they can dynamically adapt to changes in input conditions such as lighting, partial shading of the PV panel, temperature, and even material degradation.

The operation of direct algorithms using relative values—specifically by comparing current and previous measurements—enables the energy harvester to function effectively across a wide range of conditions while maintaining the highest possible extraction efficiency.

Characteristics such as high accuracy in tuning the operational point, responsiveness to dynamic changes, and high efficiency are typical features of even the simplest direct algorithms, such as Perturb and Observe (P&O)[18] and Incremental Conductance (IncCond)[19]. Of course, there are also many other algorithms, particularly those based on fuzzy logic[20] or artificial intelligence[21], which can better manage local maximum on the P-V curve generated by partially shaded PV panels or can eliminate MPPT drift[22]. However, such algorithms may require significantly more complex hardware and higher computational power.

A comparison of the properties of indirect and direct algorithms operating under uniform conditions is presented in Tab. 2.

Table 2. Comparison of selected indirect and direct MPPT algorithms under uniform conditions.

Algorithm	PV Cell Dependency	Sensor V I	Tracking Speed	Efficiency
Constant Voltage	YES	•	FAST	LOW
Open Circuit Voltage	YES	•	FAST	LOW
Short Circuit Current	YES	•	FAST	LOW
Pilot-Cell	YES	•	FAST	LOW
Perturb & Observe	NO	• •	SLOW	HIGH
Incremental Conductance	NO	• •	MEDIUM	HIGH

5. Developed On-chip Energy Harvester

We have designed an energy harvester that converts solar energy into electrical energy. This is a relatively complex microelectronic system, where the goal was to achieve the highest possible level of integration on a chip using standard 65 nm CMOS technology. Its simplified block diagram is depicted in Fig. 6. This figure illustrates parts that have been integrated onto the chip and also discrete components used externally.

Figure 6. Simplified block diagram of the proposed on-chip energy harvester.

5.1. On-chip Components

Parts of the EH system integrated on a chip are the following.

- **DC-DC Converter:** Proposed voltage converter specifically for operation with a custom designed and fully-integrated inductor on a chip [23–26] is based on the *Conventional Boost Converter (CBC)* topology [27,28]. Its core components, such as power switches, inductor and part of the input capacitor are fully integrated on the chip. The low-side power switch is controlled by PFM signal generated by control loop and the high-side power switch is driven as ideal diode with zero threshold voltage by *Zero Current Crossing Detector (ZCCD)* [29] that is part of the converter.
- **Control Loop:** The control loop adjusts the input impedance of the DC-DC converter and in this way, effectively shifts the EH operating point to a position that ensures the maximum energy extraction from the input under given conditions. This energy is transferred to the output of the energy harvester. Main components of the control loop are fully integrated on a chip. The core of the control loop consists of the following circuits:
 - **Registers:** The energy harvester is a complex electronic system integrated on a chip with targeted parameters. During the IC manufacturing, fluctuation of process occurs that may affect the EH system parameters. For this reason, we have added the capability for certain corrections/modifications of parameters using compensation banks, tuning banks and switches that can be controlled externally through register memory, i.e. via a computer. In the case of the MPPT block, it is possible to adjust the initialization parameters, change the type of internal MPPT algorithm or activate the option of connecting an external MPPT circuit implemented in a *Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA)* form. The energy harvester contains a relatively large number of registers. For better control and interaction with registers during measurement, a custom *Graphical User Interface (GUI)* was developed in Python programming language using the Tkinter tool. The developed GUI is shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7. Graphical User Interface for manipulating the registers content.

- **MPPT:** The regulation of energy transfer from the energy converter input to its output is managed by a control signal, which can be of the PWM type or PFM type. Since the entire system was designed for low-power applications, we implemented a circuit for generating a PFM signal. The generation of the proper frequency for the control signal is determined by a circuit operating on the MPPT algorithm. Depending on the algorithm type, various input information is evaluated, such as a 1-bit comparison result of voltages on the loaded and reference solar cells for *Pilot-Cell (PC)* algorithm or in the case of *Constant Voltage (CV)* and *Perturb & Observe (P&O)* algorithms, it involves 10-bit numbers from

ADC (Analog-to-Digital Converter) representing the voltage or current on the loaded solar cell. The Pilot-Cell algorithm with both adaptive step size and constant step size (adjustable via tuning registers ranging from 1 to 31) has been implemented on the chip. The output of the MPPT block is not directly the PFM control signal but rather data in two registers labeled CS and M3M, which serve as the input data for the oscillator block (OSC).

- **OSC:** A dynamically tunable relaxation oscillator is a part of the regulation loop, and its output signal frequency can be adjusted using a bank of capacitors and bank of current sources. The connection and disconnection of individual components in the banks are determined by a combination of data that the MPPT block provides to the oscillator from its own registers CS and M3M.
- **One-Shot:** Rectangular signal with 50% duty cycle generated by relaxation oscillator excites One-Shot oscillator that generates a pulse with defined width. For testing purposes, this pulse width can be further adjusted by Registers block.

5.2. Off-chip Components

- **Solar Cells:** The proposed energy harvester converts solar energy into electrical energy using a solar cell. Our goal was to design and fully integrate a DC-DC converter with its entire control loop on a chip. For this reason, we applied *IXOLAR KXOB25-14X1TF* solar cell, which was selected based on parameters such as physical dimensions and the output power. The power that the solar cell can deliver at its output is sufficient, but the voltage value is low. Based on this fact, we added another solar cell in series, achieving an adequate voltage level for the system operation. Some MPPT algorithms, such as *Open Circuit Voltage* or *Short Circuit Current*, require temporarily interrupting the supply of extracted energy to the rest of the energy harvester circuit at regular intervals for proper functioning. This functionality updates the position of actual MPP based on current lighting conditions. To ensure that such an interruption does not occur while also allowing space for the future application of the mentioned MPPT algorithms, we placed another identical assembly of solar cells next to the existing one. In this configuration, one PV cell pair serves as the source of extracted energy, while the other pair provides the reference voltage.
- **Measuring Circuits:** The proposed EH integrated circuit uses the Pilot-Cell MPPT algorithm. Decision-making occurs based on information from a voltage comparator that compares the voltage V_{PV} of a loaded solar cell pair to the reference pair voltage (representing V_{MPP} value). To test other MPPT algorithms that can be implemented in FPGA and connected to the rest of the energy harvester, it is possible to eliminate the reference pair of solar cells and replace the voltage comparator with an ADC.
- **Shunt Regulator:** The energy harvester with a feedback-free control loop aims to maximize energy extraction at the input and transfer this power to its output, resulting in an output voltage V_{OUT} from the energy harvester that is not regulated. To stabilize the output voltage level, we implemented a Shunt Regulator into the DC-DC converter, which maintains the output voltage value of 1.5 V.

5.3. Layout of the proposed Energy Harvester

The developed EH chip consists of several circuits described above (as blocks). Despite the complexity and robustness, the overall system physical dimensions are only 1.6 mm x 1 mm, and layout of the EH chip is depicted in Fig. 8a (highlighted by a red rectangle), with the most recognizable part being the inductor located at the bottom left.

The chip itself was manufactured in 65nm CMOS technology by UMC, with volume of 50 samples being manufactured, of which 10 were encapsulated. In Fig. 8b, a micro-photography of the packaged chip is shown. To evaluate and characterize the EH system and particularly, the implemented MPPT algorithms, rather comprehensive experimental measurements were performed on the prototyped samples.

Figure 8. View of the EH layout and a photo of the manufactured chip.

6. Measurement Results

To evaluate such a complex EH system through measurement of its parameters and properties, it was necessary to assemble a measurement setup shown in Fig. 9. For accurate control of the PV cell irradiation and preventing the interference from ambient lightning, a protective chamber was additionally put over solar cells during the measurement. Due to the need to measure a relatively large number of EH chip parameters, it was essential to use multiple measurement instruments such as:

- **Computer:** It is used to modify the content of control registers through a developed GUI and to store and evaluate selected measured parameters of the entire system.
- **FPGA Board (NEXYS A7 - 100T):** FPGA board is connected to the EH chip and to computer through a test board and *Universal Serial Bus (USB)* interface, respectively. Using this board, the aforementioned MPPT algorithms were externally implemented into the control loop of energy harvester. The functionality of the used FPGA board is not limited to the implementation of individual MPPT algorithms, the board also serves as read-out device for information (such as voltage and current at the energy harvester input) obtained through an ADC and the combination of CS and M3M registers that tune the relaxation oscillator frequency.
- **Oscilloscope (TEKTRONIX DPO4104B):** The oscilloscope is connected to the test board, which features an output for sensing the frequency f_{SW} of the dynamically tunable relaxation oscillator.
- **Power Supplies (KEYSIGHT EDU36311A, GW-INSTEK GPP-4323, R&S HMC8043):** The individual power supply sources serve to power the chip test board, the additional matching circuit with a two-channel ADC converter, and the illumination of the solar cells.
- **Multimeters (FLUKE 8845A, R&S HMC8012, ESCORT 3146A):** Laboratory multimeters were used to measure the output voltage V_{OUT} , the output current I_{OUT} flowing through the Shunt Regulator, the voltage value of the on-chip voltage regulator V_{LDO} , and currents flowing through the main power branches.

Before measurements of the energy harvester as a complete system, we first conducted several preliminary measurements. The aim was to obtain the radiation characteristics from the employed light source, characteristics of the solar cells connected in series under various lighting conditions, and to determine the minimum and maximum light levels at which the energy harvester still operates properly. Our measurements revealed that the

Figure 9. Measurement setup.

system operation is stable within the radiation range from 425 W/m^2 to 500 W/m^2 . Thus, these extreme radiation values were applied in subsequent measurements. We gradually applied individual MPPT algorithms (e.i. PC, P&O, CV) to the EH control loop. For the PC algorithm, which processes 1-bit information from the voltage comparator, it was possible to adjust the step size down to 1. In the case of the P&O and CV algorithms, the step size could not be lower than 15, which is due to the inadequately chosen resolution of the employed ADC. To objectively compare the behavior of the energy harvester when implementing various MPPT algorithms, tuning step for all algorithms was set to values of 15 and 31.

Since the goal of MPPT algorithms is to tune the operating point to the maximum power point, we recorded the individual positions of the operating point during the tuning process and plotted them in graphs representing the I-V characteristic and P-V characteristic shown in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 of the solar cell under two different lighting conditions, respectively. After adding the real characteristics of solar cell to the graphs, one can observe that the implemented MPPT algorithms correctly seek the maximum power point and even reach it with a certain deviation.

Figure 10. Comparison I-V characteristics under light irradiance 425 W/m^2 and 500 W/m^2 for different MPPT algorithms with tuning steps 15 and 31.

The tuning process of the operating point begins at the open-circuit voltage V_{OV} of the solar cell. By gradually adjusting the frequency of control signal for the DC-DC converter using the MPPT algorithm, the system converges to V_{MPP} value, as represented in results shown in Fig. 12a and Fig. 12b, each N value meaning one step of the convergence process. The magnitude of deviation from the actual V_{MPP} value of the solar cell is represented by the curves depicted in Fig. 13a and Fig. 13b. As already mentioned, the energy harvester with MPPT control aims to extract the maximum power from the solar cells, which in practice means that the DC-DC converter increases the output voltage V_{OUT} but the shunt regulator limits it to the value of 1.5 V, as can be observed in Fig. 14a and Fig. 14b. When the output voltage reaches this specified value, the energy converter has enough energy

Figure 11. Comparison P-V characteristic under light irradiance 425 W/m^2 and 500 W/m^2 for different MPPT algorithms with tuning steps 15 and 31.

Figure 12. Convergence of V_{IN} to V_{MPP} under light irradiance 425 W/m^2 and 500 W/m^2 for different MPPT algorithms with tuning steps 15 and 31.

Figure 13. Achieved MPP mismatch from real MPP under light irradiance 425 W/m^2 and 500 W/m^2 for different MPPT algorithms using tuning steps 15 and 31.

for its proper functioning, and the energy excess can be utilized for supplying the load or battery systems, as shown in Fig. 15a and Fig. 15b. The developed energy harvester

Figure 14. Output voltage stability under light irradiance 425 W/m^2 and 500 W/m^2 for different MPPT algorithms with tuning steps 15 and 31.

for low-power applications is controlled using a PFM signal, which drives the low-side

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Figure 15. Amount of available output power under light irradiance 425 W/m^2 and 500 W/m^2 for different MPPT algorithms with tuning steps 15 and 31.

switch of the DC-DC converter, thereby adjusting the input impedance. The control signal frequency is determined by MPPT algorithm and generated by the relaxation oscillator. The variation of the PFM signal frequency based on captured samples can be observed in Fig. 16a and Fig. 16b. Based on these graphs, it is possible to determine how long it takes for each MPPT algorithm to tune the EH system to the maximum power point. Since the frequency of the PFM signal at each point in graphs is represented by a combination of data contained in CS and M3M registers, serializing them allows for a simpler determination of how many clock cycles it takes for each MPPT algorithm to reach the MPP. These trends can be observed in Fig. 17a and Fig. 17b.

Figure 16. Relaxation oscillator frequency under light irradiance 425 W/m^2 and 500 W/m^2 for different MPPT algorithms with tuning steps 15 and 31.

Figure 17. Speed of convergence and oscillations in MPP under light irradiance 425 W/m^2 and 500 W/m^2 for different MPPT algorithms with tuning steps 15 and 31.

7. Discussion

The proposed energy harvesting system implemented in 65 nm CMOS technology proved functional during the measurement of prototyped chip samples. Since the option for external FPGA connection in the chip was implemented, we were able to incorporate

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both the P&O and CV MPPT algorithms. This allowed us to subsequently step through the entire system and gradually capture data such as the current configuration of CS and M3M registers, oscillator frequency, the input and output power, convergence speed to the MPP, and other derived parameters. We analyzed the acquired data, focusing particularly on those most influenced by the applied MPPT algorithms. In Tab. 3 and Tab. 4, we present the convergence speed to the MPP point, the voltage error at the input compared to the actual voltage at the MPP point, and the power consumption (dynamic and static) along with the chip area occupied. These results were obtained by tools in Cadence design environment. In both cases, it can be concluded that in terms of speed and step size, the Constant Voltage MPPT algorithm consistently performed the best. Regarding the error size, this parameter is primarily influenced by the tuning step size and the amount of incident radiation on the solar cells.

Table 3. Achieved results of the EH using different MPPT algorithms under irradiation $425 W/m^2$ (for tuning step 15 and 31).

Algorithm Step	PC		P&O		CV	
	15	31	15	31	15	31
Speed of Convergence [N]	57	38	146	48	49	26
Error of V_{IN} from V_{MPP} [%]	6.19	7.36	6.03	8.39	5.02	11.09
Power Consumption [$\mu W/1MHz$]	0.0089		1.5262		1.0976	
Area [μm^2]	1791		3166		1258	

Table 4. Achieved results of the EH using different MPPT algorithms under irradiation $500 W/m^2$ ((for tuning step 15 and 31).

Algorithm Step	PC		P&O		CV	
	15	31	15	31	15	31
Speed of Convergence [N]	65	41	138	54	53	27
Error of V_{IN} from V_{MPP} [%]	9.73	11.52	6.54	9.58	4.22	3.05
Power Consumption [$\mu W/1MHz$]	0.0089		1.5262		1.0976	
Area [μm^2]	1791		3166		1258	

Since neither energy consumption nor the area occupied depends on the tuning step size or the amount of extracted energy, it can be definitively concluded that the Pilot-Cell MPPT algorithm performs best in terms of energy consumption. Its consumption is more than 171 times lower than in the worst case with the P&O MPPT algorithm.

The smallest chip area among the used MPPT algorithms is that of the Constant Voltage algorithm. Its area is 2.5 times smaller than the worst case with the P&O MPPT algorithm. These results also confirm the assumptions from the theory.

The designed energy harvester represents the first iteration of our research in the development and optimization of solar-based on-chip energy harvesting, which was built on theoretical and simulation knowledge. The aim of this work was to investigate the impact of individual MPPT algorithms on selected parameters of the energy harvester. In Fig. 18, the radar chart comparing applied and evaluated MPPT algorithms in terms of main parameters is shown. The Pilot-Cell algorithm dominates with the smallest range of oscillations around the MPP (936-921 in register code) and also especially in energy consumption (dynamic + static), which is only $8.9 nW/1MHz$. The P&O algorithm has comparable properties in terms of oscillation range and error rates with other algorithms, but lags far behind in the other parameters (area, power consumption and speed of convergence). The last tested CV algorithm is essentially the PC algorithm but the decision-making occurs based on data from the ADC rather than from a voltage comparator. Such a circuit achieves the best results in convergence speed, only 26 clock cycles (and in the worst case, 53 clock

Figure 18. Spiderchart representing key properties of each inspected MPPT algorithm.

cycles). It occupies the smallest area of $1258 \mu\text{m}^2$ and its error rate ranges from 3.05 % to 11.52 %.

8. Conclusion

We have designed an energy harvester ASIC intended for low-power electronics that was prototyped using 65 nm CMOS technology by UMC. Most of the system components, such as the DC-DC converter, MPPT controller, relaxation oscillator, and one-shot oscillator have been fully integrated on the chip. Other components such as shunt regulator, evaluation and measurement circuits (i.e. a voltage comparator and ADC converter), and PV cells were used in discrete form. Different algorithms were implemented in the MPPT controller and their properties compared to find the most proper solution for increasing the overall EH efficiency. Indirect MPPT algorithms require information about the voltage of loaded solar cell (V_{PV}) and the voltage of unloaded solar cell (V_{OV}). In practice, this means that to obtain the necessary V_{OV} , it is essential to disconnect the solar cells from the rest of the circuit, preventing energy transfer for a brief moment. To avoid interrupting the supply of converted energy, we installed another identical pair of solar cells next to the existing one. This configuration provides V_{PV} from one pair of solar cells and V_{MPP} from the other. To manage the energy extraction from the aforementioned solar cell assembly, the Pilot-Cell MPPT algorithm was used. Its selected features can be configured using registers controllable via a computer. It is possible to choose whether the algorithm will operate with an adaptive or static step. In the case of a static step, the size of convergence step ranging from 1 to 31 can be selected.

From performed measurements of ASIC samples and results obtained by applying individual MPPT algorithms, we evaluated the main parameters such as area, power consumption, error from the MPP, oscillation range and speed of convergence. Based on these data, comparison of MPPT algorithms was made.

Firstly, the Pilot-Cell algorithm was analyzed. It processes 1-bit information from the comparator. In terms of energy consumption and oscillation range, it achieves the lowest values among the others, thus dominating in two key parameters out of five. The second analyzed algorithm was Constant Voltage, which is similar to PC in its operating principle. However, it works with multi-bit information from the ADC converter. Attributes such as energy consumption and oscillation range acquire higher values than PC, but as for error, speed of convergence and area, it achieves lower values. This means that it dominates in 3 out of 5 evaluated aspects. The last investigated algorithm is P&O. It is classified as a direct algorithm and uses voltage and current information from the ADC converter. This type of algorithm achieves the worst results in energy consumption, size of area and

convergence speed. As for the error of the MPP and oscillation range, the achieved values are comparable to other MPPT algorithms.

According to the analysis described above, the CV algorithm achieves the best results among the evaluated MPPT algorithms. The drawback is energy consumption and its reduction will be one of the goals of the future work. The PC algorithm also achieves excellent results, but despite the fact that it processes 1-bit information from the comparator, it requires larger area on the chip than CV. In this regard, it will also be necessary to perform optimization steps per area. The most complex analyzed algorithm P&O lags behind in several parameters. Despite the more unfavorable properties, we see a great potential for future improvements. The effort will be to get as close as possible to indirect algorithms properties, especially as for speed of convergence and power consumption.

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